

Amperometric Estimation of Cobalt in Presence of EDTA by Chloramine-T

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Amperometric titration of Co(II) with two polarised electrodes at 100 mV has been carried out with chloramine-T in presence of EDTA at pH 2.0 to 6.5. Under ordinary conditions Co(II) is not oxidisable with usual oxidants, but EDTA forms complexes with Co(II) and Co(III), lowering the redox potential of dipositive cobalt to a point where it can be titrated with even mild oxidising agents like chloramine-T.

Of the methods used for the determination of cobalt, Job's technique¹, though simple, suffers from a number of objectionable features. As cobalt is not titrable by ordinary oxidants, use has recently been made of the marked changes in the redox properties of the system in presence of complexing agents. Laitinen and Burdett² determined cobalt iodometrically in absence of interfering metals, using the corresponding carbonate complex. Recently in this laboratory, Co(II) was estimated amperometrically, using dichromate³, ceric⁴, and vanadate⁵ ions. Amperometric determination of Co(II) by chloramine-T in presence of EDTA with two polarised electrodes has been reported herein.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chloramine-T (E. Merck) solution was prepared and standardised iodometrically. Cobalt sulphate was Merck's extra pure product and its stock solution was standardised, using the same method as of Laitinen and Burdett². EDTA and other chemicals were of standard purity. Conductivity water was employed in the experiments.

The titrations were carried out with a circuit as described by Delahay⁶. Two identical platinum electrodes with an externally applied constant potential of 100 mV were immersed in the Pyrex titration cell, covered with a tight-fitting rubber stopper provided with necessary holes for nitrogen gas inlet and outlet and for the burette tip. The titrant was added from a semimicro burette and the current was measured with a galvanometer with two variable resistances, one in series and the other in parallel. During the titration, the solution was constantly stirred by a magnetic stirrer. Readings were noted at regular intervals, usually 1 min. after each addition of the titrant.

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2. *Anal. Chem.*, 1951, **23**, 1268.
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The titration mixture (20 ml) comprised Co^{2+} , a little excess over the stoichiometric quantity of EDTA, and the buffer to maintain the pH of the solution 2.0-6.5 (determined from trial experiments). The end point was determined graphically from plots of galvanometer readings against the volume of the titrant added. The results are recorded in Table I and the typical curves in Fig. 1. The accuracy and reproducibility of these titrations show its applicability even at low concentrations.

FIG. 1

A. Chloramine-T = 0.07352N. Cobalt (π) = 11.70 mg.

B. Chloramine-T = 0.01066N. Cobalt (π) = 0.6282 mg.

TABLE I

Amount of Co(π).		% Experimental error.	
Taken.	Found.	Average.	Maximum.
29.460 mg.	29.440 mg.	+0.25	+0.60
11.780	11.730	-0.33	-0.67
5.892	5.860	-0.50	+0.50
2.450	2.438	-0.90	-1.00
1.270	1.257	-1.30	-1.50
0.615	0.628	-1.50	-1.50
0.314	0.330	+4.00	+4.90

DISCUSSION

Chloramine-T was first introduced as a cheap substitute for iodine in the determination of trivalent arsenic and antimony. In aqueous solution it reacts as a hypochlorite; the advantage claimed over the latter is chiefly its stability. Chloramine-T as an oxidant⁷⁻⁸ is used in direct and indirect volumetric estimations of various compounds.

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The redox potential of the $\text{Co}^{2+}/\text{Co}^{3+}$ system is too low⁹ to be determined oxidimetrically by common oxidants under ordinary conditions. The potential is, however, changed to 0.60v when the EDTA complexes of Co^{2+} and Co^{3+} are employed, thus enabling its oxidimetric estimations even with chloramine-T.

Before the end point, both components of the reversible couple, $(\text{Co EDTA})^{2-}$ and $(\text{Co EDTA})^{-}$, are present in the solution and a considerable current flows through the system. The current of the titration curve, as anticipated on theoretical grounds¹⁰, should exhibit a maximum when the degree of completion of the titration is 0.5. The curve in Fig. 1A for the titration of $(\text{Co EDTA})^{2-}$ with chloramine-T is in agreement with the above. Fig. 1B shows how the curve changes during the trace amounts of Co(II) . The concentration of ions at equivalence point is extremely low and the limiting current, corresponding to the cathode part of the current voltage curve for the system $(\text{Co EDTA})^{2-}/\text{Co (EdTA)}^{-}$, is minimum. Beyond the equivalence point, however, the current remains constant due to absence of Co^{2+} ions and the irreversibility of the chloramine-T and its reduction product.

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